

NUTRITION FACTS about WHOLE GRAINS

Adults need 3-7
servings of whole
grains daily

Whole grains are an
excellent source of fiber

Eating at least 3 servings of
whole grains daily may
decrease risk of heart disease
and help with weight
management

Some examples of whole
grains are brown rice, quinoa,
farro, barley, popcorn,
oatmeal, and whole wheat
flours

Multigrain doesn't always mean
whole grain! Look for products that
say "100% whole grain" on the
package.

Whole Wheat Chocolate Chip Muffins

Makes: 12 muffins

Total time: 40 minutes

Ingredients:

1 stick unsalted butter, softened
1 cup sugar
2 tsp baking powder
1/2 tsp salt
1 tsp vanilla extract
2 eggs
1/2 cup milk
2 cups whole wheat flour
2 cups chocolate chips

Instructions:

1. Preheat the oven to 350°F. Lightly grease a 12-well muffin pan.
2. Beat together the butter, sugar, baking powder, salt, and vanilla.
3. Beat in the eggs, then stir in the milk.
4. Mix in the flour, and then the chocolate chips.
5. Spoon batter into muffin pan.
6. Bake for 30 minutes, or until a toothpick inserted in the center comes out clean.

One serving of whole grain looks like:

- 1/2 cup cooked brown rice or other cooked grain
- 1/2 cup 100% whole grain pasta
- 1/2 cup cooked hot cereal, such as oatmeal
- 1 slice 100% whole grain bread
- 1 oz 100% whole grain muffin
- 1 cup 100% whole grain ready-to-eat cereal

For more information, visit wholegrainscouncil.org